

**MOST DIFFICULT READING COMPETENCIES IN ENGLISH 10:
BASIS FOR DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION
OF READING INTERVENTION BOOKLET**

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Most Difficult Reading Competencies in English 10: Basis for Development and Evaluation of Reading Intervention Booklet

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Abstract

This research study aimed to develop and evaluate reading intervention booklet for grade 10 students at San Jose National High School, District II-A, Division of Antipolo City during the school year 2023-2024. The descriptive-evaluative method of research was used with the questionnaire - checklist as data gathering instrument. The developed reading intervention booklet was evaluated by the fifteen (15) Language experts consist of English Master teachers, Head Teachers, and teachers in the teaching profession for more than 10 years and (25) English teachers from San Jose National High School, Dela Paz National High School and Marcelino National High School in the Division of Antipolo City. The English teachers and expert respondents evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Booklets Very Satisfactory with regard to objectives, activities, analysis, abstraction, application, and Evaluation, with grand means of 3.88 and 3.95, respectively. In addition, there was no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed Reading Intervention Booklets in terms of Objectives, Analysis, Abstraction, Application, and Evaluation. On the other hand, there was a significant difference between the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed reading intervention booklets in terms of Activities. Comments and suggestions were given by the respondents to further improve the developed learning material.

Keywords: *reading competence, English 10, booklet*

Introduction

The need for greater knowledge is unquestionably vital in today's demanding and fiercely competitive society. That there would be severe consequences for individuals who are unable to comprehend the written word is understandable.

The search for substance and meaningful education is the definitive purpose in the Philippine educational system, especially in the K-12 curriculum goal which states that the goal of the improved K-12 Basic Education Program is to provide a workable basic education system that will generate law-abiding, productive individuals with the fundamental knowledge and abilities needed for both job and lifetime learning.

The love for reading must be acquired by every individual to have a greater preference for enjoyment and benefits. This enjoyment through reading would be attained if comprehension of the printed text took place and the understanding of the various skills in reading would be enhanced. Moreover, reading various texts with stimulating questions may challenge the learners to think. This concept may lead to developing the comprehension skills of the student which may allow more learning to happen.

Furthermore, the goal of the new DepEd MATATAG which also stands for its name seeks to give Filipino students a solid foundation by encouraging critical thinking, values formation, and holistic development. The objective is to provide students with 21st-century skills that will enable them to pursue further education, find work, and engage in active citizenship.

Unfortunately, one cannot deny the fact that the pandemic has had a devastating impact on learning. The same is true in San Jose National High School where the researcher is stationed, the number of students who were under frustration level increased to 57.14 percent since the pandemic. Moreover, the school has a target MPS or Mean Percentage Score which aims to increase every year to improve students' performance. The target mean percentage scores serve as benchmarks for educational institutions to enhance student learning outcomes and overall educational quality.

These ideas and reasons led the researcher to develop and evaluate a reading intervention booklet that would help learners especially those in need cope and manage so that they can struggle through the changes mandated by the Department of Education to address their needs. In addition, it was perceived that most of the DepEd Memoranda and objectives are to make the learners functionally literate. The reading materials will help the students understand the inscribed text through varied doings while at the same time taking into consideration their perceived difficult Most Essential Learning Competencies.

Furthermore, the K-12 curriculum aims to develop a communicative and multi-literacy learner, and in achieving this aim, the students should be exposed not only to the new technologies but also to the written text.

The researcher adapted these concepts and believed that students could attain better scholastic activity if their level of comprehension skills were strengthened. The hand-in-hand supervision of the teachers and the parents would contribute to developing a life-long learner.

Thus, this study covers the development and evaluation of reading intervention booklets in English 10 by the 15 Language experts and 25 English teachers, which aims to provide the students with a tool that can help improve their performance in reading which will

channel them to comprehension of a written text based on their most difficult reading competencies.

Research Questions

This research study aimed to develop and evaluate reading intervention booklet for grade 10 students at San Jose National High School, District II-A, Division of Antipolo City during the school year 2023-2024. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What were the top 12 most difficult reading competencies of the English 10 students based on the quarterly exam during the school year 2022-2023 as basis for developing the reading intervention booklet?
2. What was the evaluation of the Language experts and English teacher-respondents in the developed reading material for grade 10 relative to the following parts:
 - 2.1. objectives;
 - 2.2. activities;
 - 2.3. analysis;
 - 2.4. abstraction;
 - 2.5. application; and
 - 2.6. evaluation?
3. Was there a significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents in reference to the aforementioned parts?
4. What comments/suggestions were offered by the evaluators to improve the developed Reading Enhancement Booklet?

Literature Review

Language is the fundamental means of communication, it plays a crucial role in human relationships, Abdulrahman (2022). It also plays a crucial role in learning as it serves as the primary medium through which information is conveyed and understood. It facilitates communication, comprehension, and the acquisition of new knowledge and skills across various subjects and disciplines.

According to Duke and Cartwright (2021), reading difficulties arise from factors beyond decoding and listening comprehension as proposed in the simple view. Decoding and comprehension intersect significantly, and the simple view overlooks contributors like self-regulatory processes.

It is believed that when students read more frequently, their reading comprehension improves as they learn English. According to Indriani, (2019), thinking, evaluating, and learning about written texts are all part of reading. As a result, reading is becoming more and more valued as a skill since it helps people avoid misinterpreting information.

Moreover, according to Da Costa and Gutierrez (2020), reading comprehension is a deliberate, dynamic, and interactive activity that takes place prior to, during, and following the reading of a specific work of literature. The accomplished reading and comprehension skills are necessary for societal functioning. Reading is usually done with the intention of deciphering the text's meaning or message.

Meanwhile, Muico et al., 2021 pointed out that the utilization of educational materials has significantly impact the success of the educational process in general. Instructional materials are essential instruments designed to assist teachers in helping students in learning the subject and performing the activities outlined in the curriculum. By working together and interacting with words and symbols, students can enhance their reading, thinking, listening, writing, speaking, and problem-solving abilities through the use of instructional resources. Furthermore, instructional materials support students' critical and conceptual thinking in addition to offering experiences that accurately portray reality.

To further understand instructional materials, Evuti & Ali (2020), defined instructional materials as a wide range of tools that can be utilized to promote productive and successful classroom communication as instructional materials (teaching and learning).

The subsequent reviewed study was Supplemental Learning Material and Teaching Guide for Grade 8 English by Atibagos (2019). The respondents gave strongly agree and agree remarks for the developed learning material. Suggestions included were pictures must be bigger, more activities for better understanding, and more questions that aim to enhance critical thinking skills.

The study of Chavez (2019). was the next reviewed study. It was entitled Grade 10 Learners' Least Mastered Reading Competencies: Basis for the Development and Evaluation of Module on Critical Reading. Both respondents strongly agreed to all the given criteria.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-evaluative type of research. It is a type of research methodology that combines both descriptive and evaluative elements to investigate and analyze a particular subject or phenomenon. According to Siedlecki (2020) the Descriptive-Evaluative is a type of research that is used to quantify and describe a product's performance in order to determine whether or not it is practical, relevant, efficient, and effective.

Respondents

For this study, there were two sets of respondents. The first set included the 25 English Teachers from DepEd Division of Antipolo where the study was conducted particularly in San Jose National High School, Dela Paz National High School, and Marcelino National High School. They were purposely selected because of their involvement and experience in the field of English. The second set included the 15 Language Experts. Both groups were asked to evaluate the developed reading intervention booklets. The Purposive-Sampling Technique—also referred to as judging or selective sampling—was employed. This non-probability sampling method involves the researcher selecting participants according to predetermined standards that are pertinent to the study topic or goals.

Instrument

The study utilized questionnaire checklists as the primary instrument in data gathering. It consisted of criteria on Objectives, Activities, Analysis, Abstraction, Application, and Evaluation. The questionnaire was validated by ten experts and critiqued by the research adviser. Responses to the evaluation items were based on the 4-point Scale as follow: 4-Very Satisfactory, 3-Satisfactory, 2-Unsatisfactory, and 1-Very Unsatisfactory.

Procedure

Letter asking for permission to conduct this research study was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent of Antipolo City as well as the School Principal of San Jose National High School, Marcelino National High School, and Dela Paz National High School before administering the questionnaire.

The research instrument was validated, and reliability tested. A reliability coefficient of .86 was obtained which proved that the instrument has internal consistency.

The teacher-made survey questionnaire for the language experts and English teacher respondents was used to evaluate the reading intervention material. The researcher personally distributed the learning material and survey questionnaire. The respondents were fully informed about the study's purpose, and procedures as well as the confidentiality of their information and evaluation. The researcher gave enough time for the respondents to evaluate the reading intervention booklet since it consisted of twelve booklets covering the four quarters. After the evaluation, the respondents gave comments and suggestions on how to improve the material. Statistical analysis followed afterward. A summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations were formulated.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Most Difficult Reading Competencies in English 10: Basis for Development and Evaluation of Reading Intervention Booklet

Table 1. *Summary of the Computed Mean of Most Difficult Reading Competencies Per Quarter Based on the Result of the School's Quarter Tests during S.Y. 2022 – 2023*

Number	Competencies (Quarter 1)	Mean
1	Evaluate and make judgements about a range of texts using a set of criteria e.g. comparing arguments on the same topic, critiquing a short story	55.05
2	Evaluate spoken texts using given criteria e.g. fluency, tone, cohesion, correctness	56.29
3	Employ analytical listening in problem solving	56.47
Number	Competencies (Quarter 2)	Mean
4	Identify language features of an Argumentative texts	49.17
5	Formulate a statement of opinion or assertion	49.26
6	Write an exposition or discussion on a familiar issue to include key structural elements and language features	49.38
Number	Competencies (Quarter 3)	Mean
7	Critique a literary selection based on Historical approach	48.26
8	Critique a literary selection based on Reader-Response approach	51.13
9	Critique a literary selection based on Reader-Response approach	51.13
Number	Competencies (Quarter 4)	Mean
10	Compose a research report on relevant social issue	51.56
11	Observe correct grammar in making definitions	52.40
12	Give technical and operational definitions	75.11

It is clear that from Table 6, there are top 12 Most Difficult Reading Competencies in English 10 that are divided into four respective quarters and they are as follows: (1) Evaluate and make judgements about a range of texts using a set of criteria e.g. comparing arguments on the same topic, critiquing a short story, (2) Evaluate spoken texts using given criteria e.g. fluency, tone, cohesion, correctness, (3) Employ analytical listening in problem solving, (4) Identify language features of an Argumentative texts, (5) Formulate a statement of opinion or assertion, (6) Write an exposition or discussion on a familiar issue to include key structural elements and language features, (7) Critique a literary selection based on Historical approach, (8) Critique a literary selection based on Reader-

Response approach, (9) Critique a literary selection based on Reader-Response approach, (10) Compose a research report on relevant social issue, (11) Observe correct grammar in making definitions, and (12) Give technical and operational definitions.

This meant that the most difficult and most essential reading competencies listed in the table were the same lessons that were included and became the basis for the development of the Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10.

Evaluation of English Teachers and Expert Respondents on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10

Table 2. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 as regards to Objectives

Objectives The Objectives...	Respondents				
	English Teachers		English Experts		
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	
1 are well-presented and clearly stated.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS	
2 are congruent to the topics, learning tasks, and learning assessment.	3.96	VS	3.93	VS	
3 provide significant goals relevant to expected skills and knowledge.	3.92	VS	3.93	VS	
4 address the needs of the target students.	3.84	VS	4.00	VS	
5 lead the learners to the mastery of competencies in reading comprehension.	3.92	VS	4.00	VS	
	Average Mean	3.93	VS	3.97	VS
	Overall Average Mean	3.95 – Very Satisfactory			

The English teachers and language experts both evaluated the material as Very Satisfactory with average means of 3.93 and 3.97 and overall average mean of 3.95 respectively.

This meant that the Objective aspect of the developed Reading Intervention Booklets for Grade 10 was rated Very Satisfactory by English teachers and language experts, which implies that the learning objectives are well-presented, congruent to the expected skills and knowledge, address the learners' needs and can lead to the mastery of the target competency related to the reading comprehension. It also implies that excellent and appropriate objectives in learning materials serve as a roadmap, guiding both learners and teachers toward successful learning outcomes.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 as Regards to Activities

B. Activities The activities...	Respondents				
	English Teachers		English Experts		
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	
1 provide clear and precise directions/instructions for the target learners	3.88	VS	4.00	VS	
2 contain interesting tasks that catch the students' interest and attention	3.52	VS	4.00	VS	
3 elicit the understanding of the students about the lesson	3.80	VS	3.87	VS	
4 allow learners to use critical thinking skills through engaging activities	3.88	VS	3.93	VS	
5 develop the students' comprehension of the reading selection	3.88	VS	3.93	VS	
	Average Mean	3.79	VS	3.95	VS
	Overall Average Mean	3.85 – Very Satisfactory			

The data on the table indicate that both English teachers and language experts evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Booklets in English 10 in terms of Activities as Very satisfactory with the average means of 3.79 for the English teachers and 3.95 for the language experts and the overall average mean of 3.85 altogether.

The findings shown that in terms of activities, the developed Reading Intervention Booklets in English 10 has interesting and engaging tasks that catch students' attention, elicit understanding, promotes critical thinking skills towards the mastery of reading comprehension skills.

The data on the table 4 show that both English teachers and experts evaluated the developed Reading intervention Booklets in terms of Analysis aspect as Very Satisfactory with the average mean of 3.90 for teacher respondents and 3.95 for expert respondents and the overall average mean of 3.93 respectively.

With this result, it is reflected that in terms of Analysis, the developed reading intervention booklets is relevant, engaging, and aligned with the needs of the learners towards an efficient learning experience.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 as Regards to Analysis

Analysis The analysis...	Respondents			
	English Teachers		English Experts	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1 is/are appropriate to the activities	3.96	VS	4.00	VS
2 is/are relevant to the topics to be discussed	3.96	VS	4.00	VS
3 is/are suitable to the learners	3.76	VS	3.87	VS
4 engages students' critical thinking	3.84	VS	4.00	VS
5 direct and easy to understand	3.96	VS	3.87	VS
Average Mean	3.90	VS	3.95	VS
Overall Average Mean	3.93 – Very Satisfactory			

The data on the table 5 show that both English teachers and language experts evaluated the developed Reading intervention Booklets in terms of Abstraction aspect as Very Satisfactory with the average mean of 3.93 for teacher respondents and 3.92 for expert respondents and the overall average mean of 3.93.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklets in English 10 as Regards to Abstraction

Abstraction The abstraction...	Respondents			
	English Teachers		English Experts	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1 is presented in every lesson	4.00	VS	3.93	VS
2 is relevant to the target competency	3.92	VS	3.93	VS
3 contains discussion that is appropriate for the level of the target students	3.88	VS	3.93	VS
4 is appropriate and readable	3.92	VS	4.00	VS
5 contains noteworthy contexts that present the importance of the topic to one's life	3.92	VS	3.80	VS
Average Mean	3.93	VS	3.92	VS
Overall Average Mean	3.93 – Very Satisfactory			

On the Abstraction aspect, the materials provided excellent discussion that allows learners to use critical thinking, engage in the lesson actively, solve problems, improve their reading comprehension skills and creates a dynamic learning environment where they can deepen their understanding and develop important skills beyond just absorbing information

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklets in English 10 as Regards to Application

Application The application...	Respondents			
	English Teachers		English Experts	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1 provide activities that deepen the understanding of the students	3.88	VS	4.00	VS
2 are given to aid the students' knowledge, skills and attitude	3.84	VS	4.00	VS
3 engage the learners in tasks that improve their learning of the target reading competency	3.92	VS	4.00	VS
4 help learners to explore more to enhance their reading comprehension skill	3.80	VS	3.93	VS
5 are connected to all parts of the material	3.92	VS	3.93	VS
Average Mean	3.87	VS	3.97	VS
Overall Average Mean	3.91 – Very Satisfactory			

The data emphasize that both English teachers and language experts evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Booklets in English 10 in terms Application as Very Satisfactory with the average mean of 3.87 for teacher respondents and 3.97 for language expert respondents and the overall average mean of 3.91 respectively.

These findings clearly showed that in terms of application, the developed Reading intervention Booklet in English 10 provided activities that can develop students' skills, reinforce students' knowledge and retention, transfer learning to new, practical and real word situations. Moreso, it can give students continued practice which can lead to the mastery of the target most essential learning competency.

The data in table 7 present that both English teachers and language experts evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Booklet for English 10 in terms of Evaluation as Very Satisfactory with the average means of 3.86 and 3.95, and overall average mean of 3.91 respectively.

Table 7. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 as Regards to Evaluation

Evaluation The evaluation...	Respondents			
	English Teachers		English Experts	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1 gauges students' understanding of the presented lesson	3.92	VS	4.00	VS
2 provides concrete tasks that allow learner to apply the concept that they learned	3.84	VS	4.00	VS
3 contains authentic learning experiences that assess students' reading comprehension	3.68	VS	3.87	VS
4 is consistent to the content of the reading selection and other learning tasks	3.92	VS	3.93	VS
5 is congruent to the learning goal	3.96	VS	3.93	VS
Average Mean	3.86	VS	3.95	VS
Overall Average Mean	3.91 – Very Satisfactory			

These findings showed that in terms of Evaluation, the developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 promotes independent learning, has evaluation that is congruent with stated objectives, provides specific answer to measure students' learning level, allows learners a chance to reassess based on initial feedback and measures learners' abilities, interests and learning styles. The material can provide learners with a better understanding of the material being studied and the expectations associated with it.

Significant difference in the assessment of the Two groups of Respondents on the Evaluation of the Developed Reading Intervention Booklets in English 10

Table 8. Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 in terms of Objectives

Respondents	Mean	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	3.93	0.23	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Experts	3.97			

The data revealed that both English teachers and language expert respondents have the same perception/idea on the developed Reading Intervention Booklets in English 10 in terms of Objectives.

Both of the respondents agreed that by having appropriate and significant sets of objectives in the learning material, the learners will be guided as to what they should expect to learn and achieve. Furthermore, they can be motivated because they already have their sense of purpose and direction towards efficient teaching and learning.

Table 9. Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 in terms of Activities

Respondents	Mean	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	3.79	0.01	Reject Ho	Significant
Experts	3.95			

The data revealed that the English teachers and language expert respondents do not have the same perception/idea on the developed Reading Intervention Booklets in English 10 in terms of Activities.

The analysis indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in the understanding and evaluation of the two groups of respondents with regard to the activities included in the developed reading intervention booklets. There is a variation on how each group perceived the activities.

The difference on their perception could arise based on many factors such as: differences in the background, prior knowledge, learning styles and many other more.

Table 10. Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 in terms of Analysis

Respondents	Mean	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	3.90	0.27	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Experts	3.95			

The data implied that both groups found the analysis part of the developed reading intervention booklets to be similarly appropriate. This also indicated consistency in the understanding or satisfaction with this aspect of the material across the group.

Table 11. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 in terms of Abstraction*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Teachers	3.93	0.88	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Experts	3.92			

The data from the table implied that both groups of respondents perceived the abstraction part of the learning material to be relevant, well-curated, interesting, and motivates learner to actively participate in the discussion, leading to higher engagement and retention of knowledge.

Table 12. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 in terms of Application*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Teachers	3.87	0.08	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Experts	3.97			

This implied that both the English teachers and English expert respondents agreed that the application aspect of the developed learning material is appropriate and suitable that it can enable learners to apply theoretical knowledge to practical situations that will not only reinforces understanding but also cultivates critical thinking essential for the success in academic, professional and everyday contexts.

Table 13. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Reading Intervention Booklet in English 10 in terms of Evaluation*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Teachers	3.86	0.17	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Experts	3.95			

The data revealed that the two groups of respondents perceived the evaluation aspect of the developed learning material to be efficient in identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the learners. Furthermore, the evaluation part not only gauges learners' progress and performance but also informs instructional decisions, promotes continuous learning.

Comments and Suggestions Offered by the Respondents to Further Improve the developed Reading Intervention Booklets in English 10

Here the comments and suggestions offered by the two groups of respondents on the developed Reading intervention Booklets in English 10.

Comments:

The reading material is appropriate for the target learners; (b) The reading intervention material is a great learning resource since it is meant to be used for intervention; (c) The variety of strategies and engaging activities within the booklet demonstrate the teacher's creativity and dedication; (d) All parts of the material is complete, it will surely develop critical thinking and will provide assistance to learners; (e) The learning intervention material is informative and students will find it easy to answer and understand all by themselves, with this type of material they will surely improve their skills and knowledge in reading.

Suggestions:

The researcher may consider the targeted specific area of reading difficulty such as decoding information, fluency and comprehension in the development of the reading intervention booklets; (b) Text size should be consistent; (c) More engaging activities and exercises can be included in the material; (d) Rephrase the target competency; (e) Include interactive strategies approach.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

The developed interactive material is very remarkable to the experts and English teachers in terms of objectives, activities, analysis, abstraction, application and evaluation, and can really enhance the performance of the students.

The developed Reading Intervention Booklets in English 10 will become very useful among the students and teachers and may even be useful in classroom utilization.

The comments and suggestions put forth by the respondents highlighted the importance of taking into consideration the different factors and aspects in developing a Reading Intervention Booklet. These also offer practical solutions to address the challenges identified within the study and pave the way for future research endeavors.

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